

A School Visit Report

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Abstract

This report presents comprehensive overview into the academic environment, infrastructure, and administrative practices of a recent visit to Sind Madressah-Tul-Islam Fatima Jinnah Girls Secondary School situated at Karachi West. It was a very long journey and sometimes I took digital Google Map assistance as I was visiting this place for the very first time. It is currently working under a powerful nonprofit organization, Zindagi Trust. As highlighted by the Project Manager of the host school, Ms. Shahnaz Hunzai. This school is well-equipped with digital technological gadgets for young girls. It was a beautiful educational site to visit with a playground, tree shades, plant pots, beautiful creative art displayed on the board, musical classrooms, science and computer labs, clean washrooms, etc. Overall, the school visit provided deep insights into understanding Pakistan's educational system key areas including holistic education, inclusive practices, innovative pedagogical approaches, classroom dynamics, extracurricular activities, and administrative efficiency.

Introduction

On Monday, 26 May 2025 at almost 07:30 a.m. I had a golden opportunity to visit an educational institution situated in the suburbs of Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan. I travelled along with my classmates to a very polluted area of Karachi. It was very hot outside but became cooler inside the school corridors. After the course instructor took the attendance the admin personnel started the presentation about the public partnership school in an auditorium. As pointed out by the host school presenter the school modern infrastructure is due to the support and provision of not only government but also an NGO. There are almost eight schools working within one building. There are science and computer labs, an auditorium, reception, a clean cafeteria etc. within the school boundary. This was an informative session conducted by a confident and responsible school staff admin. The presentation about school ended almost at lunchtime, i.e., 12:00 p.m. It was an interesting session full of gestures, laughter, hospitality, and learning new things.

Vision Statement

To be a model government school that sets benchmarks for excellence in education, innovation in teaching, and equal opportunities for all girls, nurturing future leaders and change-makers in Pakistan.

Mission Statement

To provide quality, inclusive, and holistic education to girls from underserved communities, empowering them with knowledge, critical thinking, and life skills

to become confident, responsible, and productive members of society.

Demographic Profile

- Name: A Public Partnership School
- Type: Public-sector school
- Location: Karachi, Pakistan
- Administrative Body: A Government sector school supported by a Trust
- Gender: Female only
- Age Group: 4-16 years age girls
- Socioeconomic Background: Most of the students belong to urban mediocre or poor working-class families with diverse ethnic backgrounds

Academic Structure

- Grades: KG To Matric
- Curriculum: Sindh Textbook Board (STBB)
- Medium of Instruction: Bilingual (Urdu and English)
- Educational Board: Board of Secondary Education Karachi (BSEK)

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

A paradigm model for public sector schools. It is one of the leading government schools in Sindh working for underprivileged children.

1. Holistic Educational System

A holistic learning curriculum with Life Skills Based Education (LSBE) combining skills, arts, rhythm, and ethical citizen education.

2. Strong Infrastructure

A strong modernized building with science and computer labs, Smart classrooms, many digital gadgets facilities such as projectors, a library, music, art rooms and clean hygiene sanitation facilities.

3. Qualified Staff

The well-trained staff show organizational commitment and dedication. The teachers are provided ongoing professional development.

4. Gender Empowerment

The aim of the school is “Education for All” and “No child left behind”. The motto of this educational institute is to empower females and provide educational facilities to the needy family children.

5. Monitoring and tracking system

To improve academic and administration performance digital tracking and an evaluation system is used to keep a record of faculty.

Weaknesses

1. External Funding

The educational system is heavily running under a nonprofit organization funding that can be withdrawn at any time causing severe problems for the school.

2. Limited Resources

Many students are deprived of admission due to limited resources of school in terms of monitory facility.

3. Higher Education

Inspite being located at the main city campus the students are not provided with intermediate academic qualification that increases dropout rates and transfer.

Opportunities

1. An ideal Reform System

The educational institute can harness a unique reform system to transform education in every nook and corner of the government schools in the province of Sindh.

2. Foster e-Learning Platforms

This school can provide digital facilities to the students just like NAVTCC computer skills based professional learning programs e.g. Freelancing, Creative writing etc.

3. Internships and Scholarships

The school must provide more stipends such as internships, scholarships, laptop schemes etc. for the deserving students.

4. Partnerships with Colleges, Universities and Industries

The school must partner with higher educational institutes for future development programs for females in comparison to international standards.

Threats

1. Low Budget of Education

The school must bring to notice the allocation of budget of education for these low income and middle-class families children to support them as they are deprived of the right to educate.

2. Conservative and Extremist Society

The vicious cultural segments make it improbable to implement many advanced studies raising many issues for girls to further educate in our sophisticated thinking society still prevailing in many parts of our province.

3. Unlawful Activities

The school is located at the suburbs of the crowded city where there is a high risk of street crimes, snatching, or accidents etc.

4. Student and Teacher Turnover

The students and faculty turnover ratio have reached an alarming number due to inflation.

Resources Required

1. Human Resources

Well-qualified staff of different subjects:

- i. English and Urdu.
- ii. Social Studies and Islamiat.
- iii. Science.
- iv. Mathematics.
- v. Computer Science.

Specialists for extracurricular activities and skill development:

- i. Drawing (Arts)
- ii. Music.
- iii. Physical Education.
- iv. Special Education Needs (SEN).

Support staff such as:

- i. Librarians.
- ii. IT Supportive staff.
- iii. Lab Assistants.
- iv. Health counselors.
- v. Administrative staff body for management.

Training and development include:

- i. Regular teacher training workshops on pedagogy, technology and inclusive education.
- ii. Mentorship programs.

2. Infrastructure and Digital Resources

Smart classrooms, science and computer labs, library with the latest book editions and provision of digital resources with updated new curriculum books. Computer facility for both students and teachers. Internet availability, digital monitoring tools such as attendance and lms assessment system, e-learning platforms for advanced learners.

3. Monetary Resources

- i. Salaries for teaching and non-teaching staff.
- ii. Transportation facility and scholarships for deserving students.
- iii. A strong modern infrastructure e.g. classroom projectors signaling significant funding for the cause of better modern education.
- iv. Investment in training programs to foster skills.

4. Community and Partnership Resources

- i. Active participation of parents through parent teacher meetings and workshops.
- ii. Health camps.
- iii. Skills and vocational training.
- iv. Life skills-based learning.
- v. Career counseling.

- vi. Voluntary work such as collecting funds.

Safety and Security

1. Institution Security

- i. Strict security policy specifically for young students such as pick and drop
- ii. transport services.
- iii. Fire drills and evacuation awareness training programs.
- iv. Emergency exit caution taught and displayed in corridors as well in the classrooms.
- v. Antbullying and Harassment Policy in school. Trained student counselors, complaint suggestion boxes and helpline available, awareness campaigns on the students ethical rights, child protection through LSBE.

2. Health, Hygiene and Sanitation

- i. Clean drinking water filter water stations.
- ii. Cleaned and accessible toilets and hand washing tools for females.
- iii. First aid kits provision to every school wing.
- iv. Regular health checkups from medical doctors. Health, hygiene and sanitation campaigns in collaboration with a well-known NGO.

3. Secure Work Environment

- i. A secure learning environment for female students and staff.
- ii. Workplace Harassment Policies. (Sindh Education Department policy)
- iii. Staff and visitors ID badges and registration at entrance.
- iv. Data records being continuously updated and checked through Education department and an NGO negotiation.

Health and Wellbeing

1. Physical Fitness Programs and Support

- i. Gender-segregated washrooms with hand washing stations.
- ii. Clean filtered drinking water stations.
- iii. Maintenance and regular cleaning of the school by custodial staff.
- iv. SOPs enforcement during times of emergency such as COVID-19.
- v. Health checkups by doctors, first aid kits, referrals of hospitals or clinics for the students.
- vi. Immunization drives in partnership with the medical department.

2. Psychological Health

Trained school counselors appointed mostly through the external NGO addressing such issues:

- i. Behavioral Problems such as fatigue, stress, workload etc.
- ii. Family and Social Challenges.
- iii. Life Skills-Based Education (LSBE) included in the curriculum.
- iv. Successful campaigns on mental health issues, psychological resilience and self-grooming.

3. Nutrition, Physical Education and Extracurricular Activities

Awareness session on:

- i. Balanced diet.

- ii. WASH (Water, Sanitation and Hygiene) services.
- iii. Good Habits.
- iv. The students are not provided with regular meals but at the time of some events such as function or any specific visit healthy snacks are served.
- v. Open playground for sports such as Annual Sports Day, games such as chess, music, dance, beautiful art and crafts such as paintings and drawings displayed on softboards indicate the passionate talented girls and faculty enthusiasm and sincerity to their profession.

4. Student Councils and Peer mentoring groups

Student Councils and peer mentoring groups promote:

- i. Inclusive supportive educational environment.
- ii. Positive student mentor relationships.
- iii. Healthy and responsible school environment.

Curriculum

The school curriculum follows updated Sindh Textbook board syllabus. The classes are distributed:

- i. Primary (Grades I-V)
- ii. Middle (Grades VI-VIII)
- iii. Matric (Grades IX-X)

The medium is bilingual, but Science and Maths are primarily taught in English. LSBE, Arts, Music and Physical Education are also included in curriculum. ICT training, digital citizenship and responsive use of internet taught in higher grades. Interactive learning environment.

Bullying and Policymaking

The school aims to provide conducive learning environment for both female students and staff. The efforts are made to provide a safe environment, mitigating risks and providing ample opportunities for young energetic minds to learn, read, write and grow under the school protective umbrella.

- i. No tolerance for misconduct such as bullying, harassment or abuse.
- ii. Strict adherence to the school policy guidelines for all the students.
- iii. Suggestion boxes and staff contact provided.
- iv. Student awareness sessions such as classroom discussions on respect, kindness and compassion.

Monitoring and Evaluation

A model government school Monitoring and Evaluation department is designed:

- i. To track academic performance such as achievements.
- ii. Ensure quality education.
- iii. Evaluate reforms and research.
- iv. Promote fairness and accountable decision making.

Continuous Professional Development (CPD)

- i. Induction Training, monthly workshops.
- ii. Per week in-house session.
- iii. CPD Week on new educational tools, inclusive education and LSBE.
- iv. Digital Micro Learning short modules and Edtech tool kits.

Potential Risk and Mitigation

- i. **Safety and Security:** 24/7 security guard, local police called at the time of emergencies, ID systems etc.
- ii. **Natural Catastrophe:** Earthquake and fire drills, elevated ground system during floods, during heat waves shaded areas for protection from penetrating sunlight.
- iii. **Health Risks:** During times of outbreak such as dengue, COVID-19 health screening, SOPs are implemented, and medical facilities.
- iv. **Cyber Risks:** Firewall, digital literacy initiative and cyber bullying policy enforcement.

Education on Climate Change and 21st Century Skills

The school Climate change integration Programs include:

- i. Curriculum Integration.
- ii. Project-Based Learning and Workshops.
- iii. Awareness Campaigns.
- iv. Partnership programs.
- v. Awareness Sessions about water and energy.
- vi. Trees plantation in the school.

The school focuses on 4Cs of 21st Century Skills include:

- i. **Critical Thinking:** Extracurricular activities such as essay writing, debates, enquiry- based on science experiments.
- ii. **Communication:** Student-led assemblies, Group discussions and presentations, language learning classes.
- iii. **Collaboration:** Science tech projects, social media forums such as websites, Facebook pages, competitions etc.
- iv. **Creativity:** STEM activities, Art exhibitions, Creative writing.

Photo Gallery

Conclusion

An ideal meritorious public private partnership school for new generations. The school administration promises to empower low-income working children by transforming lives through holistic education. A conducive learning environment promoting a sense of belonging to those lower income families being deprived of the right to educate their children and forcing their agile ones to make both ends meet. In a nutshell, a ray of hope and a beacon of light for underprivileged children of our society.